

Fast recent southwestward expansion of the alien species *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* (Gastropoda, Heterobranchia) along the Mediterranean coasts of the Iberian Peninsula

Reciente y rápida expansión de la especie exótica *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* (Gastropoda, Heterobranchia) hacia el suroeste de las costas mediterráneas de la península ibérica

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ABSTRACT

Monitoring and updating the geographic spread of non-native species is of chief importance for conservation. Here we report on the range expansion of the Red Sea alien heterobranch gastropod *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* in southeast Spain, which reached the Alboran Sea (coast of the Granada province) in autumn 2023. This record represents the westernmost of the species in the Mediterranean Sea. The species is established in the studied area with a seasonal presence. It appears in summer, reaches reaches population peak in autumn, and disappears during winter. The importance of "citizen scientists" for information about the distribution of species and monitoring the status on invasive populations is stressed.

RESUMEN

El seguimiento y actualización de la distribución geográfica de las especies no nativas es de vital importancia para la conservación. Se presentan aquí la datos sobre la expansión del área de distribución del gasterópodo heterobranquio exótico del Mar Rojo *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* en el sureste de España, que llegó al mar de Alborán (costa de la provincia de Granada) en otoño de 2023. Este registro representa la cita más occidental de la especie en el mar Mediterráneo. La especie aparece estacionalmente en el área de estudio. Se empieza a observar en verano, alcanza un máximo de población en otoño y desaparece durante el invierno. Se destaca la importancia de "la ciencia ciudadana" para obtener información sobre la distribución de especies invasoras y para el seguimiento del estado de sus poblaciones.

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PALABRAS CLAVE: Especie alóctona, Mediterráneo, *Lamprohaminoea ovalis*, Península Ibérica, ciencia ciudadana.

INTRODUCTION

The Indo-Pacific heterobranch gastropod *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* (Pease, 1868) has been recorded in several Mediterranean localities under the name *Haminoea cyanomarginata* (Heller & Thompson, 1983), taxon originally described from the Red Sea. Recently, OSKARS AND MALAQUIAS (2019) have resurrected the generic name *Lamprohaminoea* to include some previously Indo-Pacific *Haminoea* species characterized by colourful patterns, including *H. cyanomarginata*. Subsequently, these authors (OSKARS & MALAQUIAS, 2020) have considered this species as a junior synonym of *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* in their systematic revision of the genus. These authors documented a remarkable genetic homogeneity throughout its wide distribution area, including samples from the Red Sea and Mediterranean, despite the variability of its colour pattern which they considered as intraspecific variation. Thus, these authors called the “purple morph” of *L. ovalis* the taxon previously described in the Red Sea as *H. cyanomarginata* (OSKARS & MALAQUIAS, 2020).

Since its first record in the Greek part of the Ionian Sea by ZENETOS ET AL. (2003), the species has spread in the Central and Eastern Mediterranean, and more recently to the Lybian waters in the African margin (RIZGALLA ET AL., 2018), and to the western basin, reaching the Balearic Islands (FERNÁNDEZ-VILERT ET AL., 2018), southeast Spain (PONTES & CROCETTA, 2020; ORENES-SALAZAR ET AL., 2021) and to the Ligurian Sea (see AZZOLA ET AL. 2022, who compile all the existing records of the species to date in the Mediterranean).

Monitoring the geographic range expansion of non-native species requires gathering all available spatiotemporal information on them. Due to the vastness

of the oceans and the difficulty of the logistics required, marine alien species that spread into new areas are often difficult to monitor, and in most marine regions, such as the Mediterranean Sea (GIAKOUMI ET AL., 2019) there are no specific procedures for their detection and tracing. This gap of knowledge has profound consequences for our ability to be informed about the spread of invaders, which is accelerating in recent decades favoured by global change (GIANGRANDE ET AL., 2020). Marine citizen science, as a partnership between members of the public and the academic scientists, offers a promising avenue to overcome these challenges (ENCARNAÇÃO, TEODÓSIO & MORAIS, 2021). Where properly executed, citizen science can provide high-quality and useful data that can be used for policy and decision-making, more cost-effectively than traditional forms of science (HYDER ET AL., 2015; ACEVES-BUENO ET AL., 2017).

Here, we combine public and scientific data to report new records of the heterobranch gastropod *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* in the southeast and south Spanish peninsular coast in order to document in detail the ongoing southward and westward expansion of the species in this area of the Mediterranean.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A compilation of all existing records on the occurrence of the Red Sea alien mollusc *L. ovalis* in the Spanish peninsular coast between the coasts of Murcia (SE Spain) and Granada (in the Alboran Sea) were gathered (ca. 400 km of coastline, Fig. 1). The data obtained originate from our own observations on routine dives in this area and from those pro-

Figure 1. Localities where *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* has been observed in the Spanish coasts. In yellow previous records, in red present records. #1-2: Illa del Toro and Cala d'Or, Mallorca, Balearic Islands (December 2017), #3: El Farallon Islet, Murcia (July 2020), #4: Nova Tabarca, Alicante (August 2020), #5: Ibiza, Balearic Islands (September 2020), #6-7: several points around Cabo de Palos, Murcia (September 2021); #8: Calabardina, Águilas, Murcia (October 2022), #9: several localities in Cabo de Gata-Níjar, Almería (October 2022); #10: Calahonda, Granada (October 2023), #11: Motril harbour, Granada (October 2023), #12: Almuñecar, Granada (October 2023), #13: La Herradura, Granada (October 2023), #14: Maro-Cerro Gordo, Granada (November 2023). The data correspond to the first observation in each locality. For additional information see Table I.

Figura 1. Localidades donde se ha observado Lamprohaminoea ovalis en las costas españolas. En amarillo citas previas, en rojo nuevas citas. #1-2: Illa del Toro and Cala d'Or, Mallorca, islas Baleares (diciembre 2017), #3: islote El Farallon, Murcia (julio 2020), #4: Nova Tabarca, Alicante (agosto 2020), #5: Ibiza, islas Baleares (septiembre 2020), #6-7: varios puntos en Cabo de Palos, Murcia (septiembre 2021); #8: Calabardina, Águilas, Murcia (octubre 2022), #9: varias localidades en Cabo de Gata-Níjar, Almería (octubre 2022); #10: Calahonda, Granada (octubre 2023), #11: puerto de Motril, Granada (octubre 2023), #12: Almuñecar, Granada (octubre 2023), #13: La Herradura, Granada (octubre 2023), #14: Maro-Cerro Gordo, Granada (noviembre 2023). Las fechas corresponden a la primera observación en cada localidad. Para información adicional ver Tabla I.

vided by other divers who have been photographing the species, from summer 2020 to winter 2023.

RESULTS

Table I provides the compilation of localities and data where observations were made. The observations on the species are detailed below chronologically and from north to south (Fig. 1).

The first observation of *L. ovalis* in the area covered by the present study

was on July 3, 2020, in El Farallon Islet (#3 in Fig. 1). Two specimens of about 10 mm in length were observed at 10 m depth while mating on a rocky bottom with an entangled matrix of algae dominated by *Caulerpa cylindracea* Sonder, 1845 and *Dictyota* sp. This observation should therefore be considered as the first record of the species in the Iberian Peninsula.

One year later, on September 16, 2021, a high number of individuals were observed around Cabo de Palos (#6), 10 km south of El Farallon Islet, with densi-

Table I. List of localities, coordinates and dates of first observation of *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* in southeastern Spain.

Tabla I. Lista de localidades, coordenadas y fechas de la primera observación de *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* en el sureste de España.

ID	First record	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Reference	Author of the record
#1	Dec 2017	Illa del Toro, Mallorca, Balears	39°27'41.8" N	2°28'17.5" E	Fernández-Vilert <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Rubén Castrillo and Rosa Taberner
#2	Dec 2017	Cala d'Or, Mallorca, Balears	39°21'55.1" N	3°14'09.6" E	Fernández-Vilert <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Sébastien Scala and Javier Atero Cano
#3	Jul 2020	El Farallon, Murcia	37°43'53.4" N	0°41'55.8" W	This paper	Victor Orenes
#4	Aug 2020	Nova Tabarca Island, Alicante	38°10'20.1" N	0°29'01.1" W	Ragkousis <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Daniel Muñoz
#5	Sep 2020	Ibiza Island, Balears	38°51'58.9" N	1°15'35.5" E	Ragkousis <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Miquel Pontes and Fabio Crocetta
#6	Sep 2021	Cabo de Palos, Murcia	37°38'10.8" N	0°41'18.8" W	This paper	Victor Orenes and Javier Ferrer
#7	Oct 2021	Cabo de Palos - Islas Hormigas MPA, Murcia	37°38'24.1" N	0°40'43.7" W	This paper	Victor Orenes and Javier Ferrer
#8	Sep 2022	Calabardina, Murcia	37°25'21.9" N	1°29'56.3" W	This paper	La Almadra Diving Center
#9	Oct 2022	Cabo de Gata-Níjar Natural Park, Almería	36°46'11.1" N	2°04'26.6" W	This paper	ISUB Diving Center, Diego Moreno and Agustín Barrajón
#10	Oct 2023	Calahonda, Granada	36°42'10" N	3°24'41" W	This paper	Francisco Sedano
#11	Oct 2023	Motril Harbour, Granada	36°42'53" N	3°30'32" W	This paper	Luis Sánchez Tocino
#12	Oct 2023	Punta del Vapor, Granada	36°43'22" N	3°43'36" W	This paper	Luis Sánchez Tocino
#13	Oct 2023	La Herradura beach, Granada	36°43'39" N	3°44'08" W	This paper	Luis Sánchez Tocino
#14	Nov 2023	Maro-Cerro Gordo Natural Site, Granada	36°43'51" N	3°46'16" W	This paper	José María Juárez

ties of up to 15 specimens per 10 cm². All size classes were represented, from few millimetres to the largest sizes (around 12 mm in extended length). Many of the larger specimens were mated in pairs. The species was found on rocky substrates covered by algae, mainly on *Jania virgata* (Zanardini) Montagne, 1846 and *Halopteris scoparia* (Linnaeus) Sauvageau, 1904. After the first sighting in Cabo de Palos, the species was observed in the following months within the Marine Reserve of Cabo de Palos-Hormigas Islands (#7) in several locations (Cala

Escalera, Cala Fria, Bajo de Testa, Bajo de Piles I and Bajo de Fuera). *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* was found between 5 and 33 m depth, in different types of habitats, from hard bottoms covered with algae, to soft detritic bottoms, and even under stones (Fig. 2A).

In September 2022 a single individual of *L. ovalis* was sighted at Calabardina (#8), 75 km south of Cabo de Palos. In the same place, and one year later (autumn 2023), a population boom was observed. The species was then found mainly on man-made structures (ropes

Figure 2. Individuals of *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* observed at Cabo de Palos - Islas Hormigas Marine Reserve, Murcia (A), and La Herradura, Granada (B).

Figura 2. Ejemplares de Lamprohaminoea ovalis observados en la Reserva Marina de Cabo de Palos - Islas Hormigas, Murcia (A), y La Herradura, Granada (B).

and anchors) and on rocky bottoms covered by turf-forming rhodophytes.

In October 2022 the species was observed for the first time in the coast of the Almería province, near the town of San José, within the Natural Park of Cabo de Gata-Níjar (#9). Some specimens, 6-10 mm in length, were seen on a rocky bottom covered by photophilic algae between 6 and 12 m (Fig. 3), exhibiting trailing behaviour. The species was observed during the same autumn in several localities of this marine protected area between Isleta del Moro and San José (Cueva del Francés, Las Hermanicas, La Atalaya and Punta del Castillo). In the following months, the presence of the species decreased notably. Several specimens were observed in Punta del Castillo on December 20, 2022, and just two individuals in February 2023. No further observations were made in the area until autumn of 2023. In September 2023, some specimens began to appear in Cueva del Francés, and by October 2023 the species was present in all the previous localities and in two new ones (Cala Higuera and Los Burros). Most specimens in this area (up to 10 mm in length) were found between 10 and 17 m depth on photophilic algae, frequently *H. scoparia*.

In October 2023, the species was found for the first time west of the Almería-Oran oceanographic front (in the Alboran Sea), in the province of Granada (Fig. 2B).

Between October and November 2023, more than 100 specimens have been found in several localities (#10 Calahonda, #11 Motril Harbor, #12 Punta del Vapor and #13 La Herradura, Fig. 1), mainly on shallow bottoms with photophilic algae down to 10 m depth. The latest record of the spread of the species was made in late November 2023, when the species was found in Maro-Cerro Gordo Natural site (#14).

All the specimens observed in the study area belong to the so called 'purple morph' of *L. ovalis* (OSKARS & MALAQUIAS, 2020), characterized by white background with solid purple lines along edges of cephalic shield, parapodial and pallial lobes, and scattered yellow round blotches (Fig. 2). The shell is globose, translucent, with a smooth surface and almost imperceptible growth lines (Fig. 4A). The aperture is wider in the anterior region and rises above the spire; the columellar callus is only slightly developed. The species often exhibits trailing and mating behaviour (Fig. 4B).

DISCUSSION

After the firsts record of *L. ovalis* in the western Mediterranean, in the Balearic Islands (FERNÁNDEZ-VILERT *ET AL.*, 2018), the species has spread along

Figure 3. Underwater environment in which *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* is typically found in the study area (San José, Almería, 10 m depth). The arrow indicates the location of one specimen.

Figura 3. Ambiente típico en el que se ha encontrado *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* en el área de estudio (San José, Almería, 10 m de profundidad). La flecha indica la localización de un ejemplar.

the Mediterranean coast of the Iberian Peninsula (PONTES & CROCETTA, 2020; ORENES-SALAZAR ET AL., 2021; present study) where it seems now established. The arrival of *L. ovalis* to the northern Alboran Sea (coast of Granada) was very recent (autumn 2023) as evidenced by the absence of observations in the frequent and routine dives that have been carried out in the area for many years. Hence, *L. ovalis* probably has a great capacity for larval dispersal since it has been able to cross two oceanographic fronts in less than three years, first (2020-2022) the Cartagena-Tenes Front (HERNÁNDEZ-CARRASCO & ORFILA, 2018), and later (2022-2023) the Almería-Oran Front. The latter front is known to act as a gene flow barrier between the Alboran Sea and the remaining Mediterranean basin, as observed for some marine species (PATARNELLO, VOLCKAERT & CASTILHO, 2007; EL AYARI ET AL., 2019). Future surveys are necessary to determine if the

species expands to other areas of the Alboran Sea and if it reaches the Strait of Gibraltar.

In the study area *L. ovalis* was found in a wide bathymetric range from 5 to 33 m depth, mainly on rocky bottoms covered by photophilic algae, but also on man-made structures and on detritic bottoms. The vast majority of specimens were observed in the autumn months, while some of them were observed in summer and very few in winter. These data coincide with the observations of other authors, and with the seasonality pointed out by LOMBARDO & MARLETTA (2021), who noted that *L. ovalis* populations in eastern Sicily appeared in summer, reached their peak in autumn, and disappeared at the end of winter.

All the specimens observed in the present study belong to the 'purple morph' (*sensu* OSKARS & MALAQUIAS, 2020), described previously as *Haminoea cyanomarginata* by HELLER & THOMPSON

Figure 4. *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* (Las Hermanicas, San José, Almería). A: shell; B: two specimens in mating behaviour in laboratory.

Figura 4. *Lamprohaminoea ovalis* (Las Hermanicas, San José, Almería). A: concha; B: dos ejemplares en cópula en laboratorio.

(1983). This colour morph seems to be restricted to the Red Sea and Mediterranean Sea. In turn, other different colourful patterns common throughout the species' wide range in the Indo-Pacific have not been found in the Red Sea and Mediterranean. Despite these clear geographical differences in colour pattern, the different morphs resulted genetically homogeneous by phylogenetic analyses, using DNA sequences of the cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (OSKARS & MALAQUIAS, 2020). Further genetic analyses with other molecular markers are necessary to clarify the taxonomic status of the purple colour morph.

Since this alien gastropod was first recorded in Greek waters (in Porto Germano) and there are no records in the easternmost coasts of the Mediterranean (Israel and Lebanon), the hypothesis that *L. ovalis* has entered the Mediterranean by shipping transport instead of being a true Lessepsian immigrant is reinforced, as has been pointed out by FERNÁNDEZ-VILERT *ET AL.* (2018). The easternmost record of the species was in Cyprus in August 2016 (CROCIETTA & ANDREOU, 2018), fifteen years after the first sighting in the Korinthiakos Gulf, Greece (ZENETOS *ET AL.*, 2003). Anyway, since the 'purple morph'

seems not to be present in the Indo-Pacific, it is more likely that the species reached the Mediterranean Sea through shipping from the Red Sea, instead of natural dispersal via Suez Canal. However, the fast spread of the species within the Mediterranean was more likely achieved through larval dispersal since the species occurs in many places far from ports.

The striking colour pattern of *L. ovalis* contrasts with the cryptically dull colour of the true *Haminoea* species, including that of the allochthonous *H. japonica* Pilsbry, 1895, probably introduced in the Mediterranean Sea along with cultures of the bivalve *Ruditapes philippinarum* (A. Adams & Reeve, 1850) (ZENETOS *ET AL.*, 2003 as *H. callidegenita*), and with that of the autochthonous European species of this genus. MOLLO *ET AL.* (2008) noted the presence of deterring secondary metabolites produced *de novo* in *L. ovalis* (as *H. cyanomarginata*), which implies aposematism (detering predators) and favours its expansion in new geographical areas.

The fact that there are many more records of this colour morph of the species in the Mediterranean than in the Red Sea, where it was originally described (as *H. cyanomarginata*) may be

an artifact since the colourful sea slugs are particularly suitable for their monitoring through citizen science, because they are very attractive for divers and underwater photographers (HOEKSEMA & YONOW, 2021).

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